

Differing Space and Time Interactions in Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 20, 2021

The wavefunction for a quantum free particle is $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. In this case, E and p are linked through either $E = p^2/2m$ (nonrelativistic case) or $E = \sqrt{p^2 + m^2 c^4}$ (relativistic case $c=1$). We argue that there are different interactions involved with E and p . P (momentum) is energy flow and is involved in impulse type interactions with a potential usually $V(x)$. For $V(x,t)$ matters are more complicated, but will also be discussed. The impulse hits are associated with $\exp(ipx)$ and lead to interfering plane waves and an overall crest-trough spatial scenario. There is a kinetic energy (nonrelativistic case) associated with each p , but a new overall energy E_n (n = eigenlevel) is created which yields the free form $\exp(-iE_n t)$. This energy is linked to the cycling of $\exp(ipx)$'s. It is also part of the new mass of the bound state system i.e. $m_0 + E_n$. This new system could be considered as an overall free particle and obtain a new overall momentum. (The initial bound state has 0 overall momentum.) Thus, time and space parts of the wavefunction behave in very different manners due to the nature of the interaction even though there is a link between $1/E$ and cycling of $\exp(ipx)$ terms. We call this case an impulse or space based type of interaction.

It is also possible to have a time based interaction i.e. the absorption of a photon, phonon etc. In such a case, there is momentum conservation and so the whole system receives a new momentum, but this is usually ignored. The main effect is for the system to move from one bound state $E(n_1)$ to another $E(n_2)$. This has consequences on the spatial density and cycling of $\exp(ipx)$ terms in the wavefunction, but is not an impulse interaction in space. In the case of a system: $W(x,t) = \sum_n a_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$, one has time based interactions which knock the system from one bound state to another (as in heat bath interaction). Again there are links between each E_n and the spatial density, but there is an overall spatial density $\rho(x,t)$ and average energy $\langle E \rangle(x,t)$ which depends on the interference of $\exp(-iE_n t)$ terms. (This disappears if one integrates over all x .) This is similar to the diffraction/interference spatial pattern, but in time.

In the impulse scenario for $a(p) = a(-p)$ one has cross terms in the spatial density of $\cos((p_i - p_j)x)$ which create the crest/trough pattern seen. For the heat bath time type interaction, there exist $\cos((E_i - E_j)t)$ type terms if $a_n(E_n) = a^* n(E_n)$ which are linked to the energy $E_i - E_j$ of the intermediary photon/phonon etc and its time period. Thus in both cases, the quantum crest/trough pattern (in space or time) seems to be linked to the momentum or energy transfer. The energy transfer is known to be linked to periodic objects (photons/phonons) and it seems the momentum transfer $p_i - p_j$ also has a similar periodicity, but in space. It is almost as if these "entities" are creating the unusual quantum crest/trough patterns.

The Quantum System As A Kind of Potential

We have argued in previous notes that a quantum particle or system acts as a tiny potential system. A free particle with momentum p and some kind of associated force (e.g. a charge) is able to deliver an impulse. Furthermore, it has an intrinsic probability pattern due to $\exp(ipx)$ (within a wavelength range or so) which creates a kind of pressure distribution even though

there is one value of p . If $\exp(ipx)$ interacts with two slits or with a potential, it receives impulse hits which yield a series of interfering (probability addition) $\exp(ipx)$'s which in turn yields a new potential profile (the wavelength $W(x)$) of the particle. For a free particle, there is an associated $\exp(-iEt)$ which is often overlooked because it is not used much in bound state calculations. For example for state n , one has $W_n(x,t) = \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ and it is only $W_n(x)$ which is decomposed into a Fourier series. The $\exp(-iE(p)t)$ of the $\exp(ipx)$ terms has disappeared to make way for a new energy cycling $\exp(-iE_n t)$. If a single particle is knocked out of the bound state, however, it will have a specific p and $E = p^2/2m$ (nonrelativistic) and the wavefunction becomes once again $\exp(-ipp/2m t + ipx)$. Thus there is a time cycling or frequency associated with $\exp(ipx)$, but it is ignored in a stochastic impulse scenario i.e. hits with a potential $V(x) = \sum \text{over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ because a new resonance with an E_n and no net overall momentum is produced. This cycling must be described by the wavefunction and so spatial and time portions of the wavefunction appear as different although they are connected. For example, writing the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ as Fourier series yields:

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \sum \text{over } k V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p) \quad ((1))$$

There is no time in this equation, but there is a conversion of various $a(p-k)$ i.e. $\exp(i(p-k)x)$ into $\exp(ipx)$. Given the weights of $a(p-k)$, higher $p-k$ terms suggest higher momenta or speeds and a faster cycling time linked to E_n we argue.

Thus in the presence of a potential $V(k)$, impulse hits which govern a nonlocal spatial pattern occur in such a way as to create a constant energy at each point x . This is like the establishment of a new "mass" as the bound system has no overall momentum. As a result, the time portion of the wavefunction must reflect the existence of this new masslike state and so is $\exp(-iE_n t)$. This new mass system may then receive an overall momentum and become a moving system. Its mass energy is $m_0 + E_n$. Thus impulse hits due to $\exp(ikx)$ from a potential lead to a spatial interfering system.

The Case of $V(x,t)$

Many time-dependent Schrodinger equation problems involve a time-dependent potential. In the above section we discussed impulse hits from $V(x) = \sum \text{over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and argued that these lead to spatial impulse hits on a quantum particle involving only $\exp(ipx)$. A new overall energy E_n is created and holds at each x i.e. $[-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W + V(x) = E_n$. It is linked to the cycling frequency of the various $\exp(ipx)$. In the case of $V(x,t)$, one does not expect energy to be constant in time at a point x as one may choose t_1 and perform a Fourier expansion $V(x,t_1) = \sum \text{over } k V_k(t_1) \exp(ikx)$. If the quantum particle is seen as creating a kind of potential to counteract $V(x,t)$, it must do so now in time and space.

The Case of $W(x,t) = \sum \text{over } n a_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$

There is also the case of a purely time related interaction as in:

$$W(x,t) = \sum \text{over } n a_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x) \quad ((2))$$

In this case, each state $W_n(x)$ has a spatial density profile linked to a cycling time proportional to $1/E_n$. The system, however, receives time interactions e.g. photon/phonon etc absorptions/emissions to jump from one state to another. In the case of impulse hits from $V(x)$, $\exp(ipx)$ terms interfere, but here it is $\exp(-i E_n t)$ terms which interfere. One may note that E_n is an average energy (it contains fluctuations of instantaneous kinetic energies associated with various $\exp(ipx)$ terms). As a result:

$$\text{Spatial density}(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t) \quad ((3a))$$

and

$$\text{energy}(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n_1, n_2 \quad a_{n_1}^*(E_{n_1})\exp(iE_{n_1}t)W_{n_1}^*(x) \quad a_{n_2}(E_{n_2})\exp(-iE_{n_2}t)W_{n_2}(x) \quad ((3b))$$

and are time dependent. Integrating over dx , however, removes this time dependence. Nevertheless, it seems that one should be able to experimentally detect the time dependence of density at a point x . For a system with only E_1 and E_2 , one should observe time dependent terms of $\cos((E_1-E_2)t)$ if $a_{n_1}^*=a_{n_2}$. This is a purely quantum phenomenon linked directly to the spatial crests/troughs of two slit interference or bound states (e.g. oscillator states) except the variation is in time. It suggests that there is a physical oscillation associated with energy. The cycling of $\exp(ipx)$ in a certain E_n bound state already suggested such a periodicity in time, but with the time interference problem one may see an analogy with the two slit interference situation.

Comparison of the Impulse Single Bound State Scenario and the Photon/Phonon Heat Bath Scenario

In the above sections, the bound state wavefunction $W_n(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is considered as well as the photon/phonon heat bath wavefunction $W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \quad a_n(E_n)\exp(-iE_n t)W_n(x)$. If one calculates the density W^*W of both, one notices that cross terms are similar i.e.

$$\cos((p_1-p_2)x) \exp(-iE_n t) \quad a(p_1)a(p_2) \quad \text{for } a(p)=a(-p) \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{and } \cos((E_1-E_2)t) \quad a_1(E_1)a_2(E_2)W_1(x)W_2(x) \quad \text{for } a^*=a \quad ((4b))$$

In the first case, the period (i.e. wavelength in space) is linked to p_1-p_2 i.e. the momentum change during the impulse. In the second case, E_1-E_2 is the energy of the absorbed/emitted photon/phonon i.e. the change in energy during the time interaction. In the momentum case, p_1-p_2 takes on every value and so an extra constraint equation related to average energy together with boundary conditions is needed. This leads to quantization of E_n with the equation being the time independent Schrodinger equation $[-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}]W + V = E_n$ which is a conservation of average energy equation. In it one may see two forms of energy, kinetic and potential and so E_n is a combination of both i.e. a new kind of resonance is created. In the heat

bath scenario $W_n \exp(-iE_n t)$ already represents a quantum bound state. An extra constraint equation with boundary conditions is not needed. This is the scenario which allows one to jump from one bound state to another with quantized energy units.

Periodicity is only seen in spatial density if there are cross terms with different momentum or energy values. For a bound state, there is one energy so the cross terms are due to momentum differences, while for the $W(x,t)$ state there are both cross terms due to energy differences and momentum differences within bound states. It is interference in both cases which allows the intrinsic quantum periodicity (crests and troughs) in either time or space to be observed in the density.

One may further note that $E_1 - E_2$ represents the energy of a photon/phonon etc which itself is periodic in time. Given that different impulse hits in a bound state yield density cross terms of $\cos((p_1 - p_2)x)$ for $a(p) = a(-p)$, it is suggestive that the impulse momentum change $p_1 - p_2$ is through a periodic object with wavelength proportional to $1/(p_1 - p_2)$. This seems to be in keeping with the idea that objects (e.g. photons, a quantum particle and a potential) all seem to contain periodicity and to be involved in interactions. As a result, the quantum spatial density seems to contain periodic terms associated with momentum or energy terms as if they were separate entities within the system.

Meaning of Time In the Bound State and Heat Bath States

Time in classical mechanics seems to differ from that in quantum bound states. For oscillator solutions, the classical frequency for all energy states is the same namely $\omega = 2\pi \cdot 3.14 \cdot \text{frequency}$, but in quantum mechanics, these states have different energies $E_n = \hbar \omega (n + 0.5)$ and periods proportional to $1/E_n$. We have argued that these periods are associated with time resolution i.e. the time needed for cycling i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ impulse hits with $\exp(ikx)$ terms within $V(x)$ to create the resonance. Thus time resolution is based on a specific cycling process i.e. $((1))$. Interactions on the other hand are based on impulses between the quantum particle and the potential and are described in terms of momentum changes and not in terms of energy. On average, however, one must make statements about energy and this leads to the average energy conservation equation or the time-independent Schrodinger equation. For a specific bound state, however, one does not see this cycling in the spatial density because $\exp(iE_n t) \exp(-iE_n t) = 1$.

In the case of a $W(x,t) = \sum_n a_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$, spatial density and average energy changes in time at various x points (but these time changes disappear if one integrates over dx because W_n are orthonormal.) The frequencies, however, seem to be those of the absorbed/emitted photons/phonons etc. and are again not linked to classical motion. They also do not seem to be particularly linked to cycling times proportional to $1/E_n$ except for the fact that the photons/phonons must take energies of $E_{n1} - E_{n2}$.

Thus the periodicity either in the bound state impulse picture i.e. $\cos((p_1 - p_2)x)$ or in the time interaction heat bath $\cos((E_1 - E_2)t)$ seem to both be linked to periodicity in the change in p or E due to the particular interaction i.e. a spatial or time interaction. In the time case, it seems that time dependence, i.e. the periodic $\cos((E_1 - E_2)t)$ is related to the photon part of the interaction with $W_1^*(x)W_2(x)$ representing the quantum particle spatial density cross term. The product: $\cos((E_1 - E_2)t)W_1^*(x)W_2(x)$, however, seems to be unusual with spatial density disappearing becoming negative then reappearing at a particular x during a time cycle linked to the period

$1/(E_1 - E_2)$. Thus it seems that it is the time resolution of the photon/phonon associated with the cross term which governs the time evolution of the spatial density at a given point.

As a result, peculiar interference patterns (crests and troughs) which appear in space (bound states, two slit interference) and in time (heat bath wavefunctions) seem to be linked to periodicities based on the various momentum ($p_i - p_j$) or energy ($E_i - E_j$) differences. As noted in the case of $E_i - E_j$ one has a physical periodic entity (a photon or phonon etc), but for $p_i - p_j$ the impulse change might also be a periodic entity i.e. a momentum transfer from the potential to $\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider two different kinds of interactions which lead to different types of quantum interference. In the first case, that of a bound state, interactions involve impulse hits between a potential $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and a particle $\exp(ipx)$'s. Impulse hits involve momentum transfers and so one must consider the momentum part of the free particle wavefunction i.e a distribution of these. Overall, however, there are two energies represented, that of average kinetic energy and $V(x)$ and so a constraint equation with boundary conditions (extra constraints) is needed. The constraint is one of average energy, so one has a conservation of average energy equation or the time-independent Schrodinger equation. The density $W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ involves cross terms of $\cos((p_i - p_j)x)$ so it is as if the impulse momentum transfers $p_i - p_j$ are creating the unusual crest/trough scenario.

Similar ideas seem to carry over to the heat bath wavefunction picture i.e. $W(x,t) = \sum_n a_n(E_n)\exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ where one has time interactions (not spatial impulses) and there is no new potential term only photons/phonons supplying the extra energy $E_i - E_j$ which is quantized. Interference cross terms yield $a_i(E_i)a_j(E_j) \cos((E_i - E_j)t)$ if $a^*(E_i) = a(E_i)$ which is linked to the period $E_i - E_j$ of the photon or phonon i.e. the interaction intermediary. Thus, the crests/troughs in time seem to be linked to the photon or phonon at a particular x . Integrating over all dx eliminates these time dependencies because W_n are orthonormal.